

α,β -Cyclopent-[1-amino]-4,5-eno- β -thio(3'-ethyl-4'-propyl-11',11',12'-trimethyl)tridecano-pyrrol. Tentatively identified in Darius Crude

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A substituted pyrrole alkyl sulphide has been isolated from the heavy end (300-470°) of Darius crude. The structure of the compound was elucidated, principally, from the mass spectral fragmentation pattern, supplemented by the ir and nmr spectral data.

THE sulphur and nitrogen compounds in crude oils are of importance because of their deleterious effects¹ during producing, processing and refining. A knowledge of the structural character of these compounds is essential for the efficient processing and use of various boiling fractions of the crude oils particularly in the higher boiling fractions which represent a large percentage of the original crude and have become important contributors to future petroleum requirements. Although routine procedures are now available for the characterisation of heteroatomic constituents in the fraction boiling upto 250°, information regarding the nature of these compounds in higher boiling fractions is negligible²⁻⁵. Little work has been done on understanding the nature of non-hydrocarbon constituents containing both nitrogen and sulphur atoms in the same molecule. In the present investigations chromatography on silica gel and alumina was employed extensively in order to minimise the formation of any artifacts.

Experimental

Darius crude is from the Darius offshore field in Iran. Silica gel (B.D.H. Poole England) and Alcoa F-20 alumina were used for preparation of residue A and A₂, respectively while tlc grade silica gel with binder (B.D.H., India) was used for rest of the elution and preparative tlc. Quantitative determination of sulphur was carried out using Bomb (ASTM⁶) and Wickbold (ASTM⁷) methods. Ir spectrum (neat) of the compound was run on a Perkin Elmer 577 spectrophotometer, the nmr spectrum (CCl₄) on a 100 MHz Varian spectrometer and the mass spectrum was obtained at 70 eV using a Hitachi RMV-6E instrument.

The crude oil (152.30 kg) was topped upto 300° in a pilot distillation unit working at atmospheric

pressure at a still temperature of 250°. The residue above 300° was vacuum flashed in a continuous vacuum flash unit at a rate of 3.25 dm³ h⁻¹, flash temperature 275°, vapour temperature 250° and pressure 1-1.5 mm/Hg when the 300-470° cut (29.87% by weight) was obtained.

Chromatography of the 300-470° boiling fraction (15 g) was done on a column (240 × 4.5 cm) of silica gel (1.5 kg, A/S=100). Elution was done successively with hexane, benzene, methanol and acetic acid (Fig. 1). Residue A obtained from benzene eluate (25%; S=9.66%) was further chromatographed over activated Alcoa alumina F-20. Elution with 12 dm³ of benzene-hexane (1 : 1) initially at a very slow rate and then at a fast speed developed the column into six coloured zones. Each zone was sliced out as shown in Fig. 2 and extracted by Soxhlet separately with benzene followed by methanol. Residue A₂ (Fig. 1) showed eight spots with R_f values 0.92, 0.85, 0.79, 0.70, 0.65, 0.57, 0.52 and 0.39. This was resolved on columns (20 × 4.5 cm) with a perforated disc (~1.25 cm) from the base by ascending chromatography by developing in diisopropyl ether-isooctane (1 : 19). The developed column was sliced into fourteen slices each of which was separately extracted with boiling chloroform and the residues obtained were designated as B₁, B₂, B₃, ... B₁₄.

Each of the B₁-B₁₄ fractions was separately eluted over silica gel with diisopropyl ether (C₁-C₁₄), methanol and chloroform successively. The methanol eluates of the fourteen fractions were combined and so also their chloroform eluates. The residue C₁ was chromatographed on a silica gel (tlc grade) column (5.0 × 1.0 cm) by elution successively with heptane and heptane-diisopropyl ether mixtures (1 : 99, 1 : 49, 1 : 24 and 1 : 9).

Fig. 1

Fig. 2

Fractions of 1 ml each were collected and qualitatively analysed by tlc by developing in diisopropyl ether-isooctane (1 : 19). Those similar in behaviour were mixed and were found to be single component or a mixture of two (the latter yielded pure components after similar treatment). The fractions C₅-C₆ were also treated similarly to yield four components with R_f values 0.79, 0.73, 0.68 and 0.62

with yellow fluorescence under uv light. The four compounds showed single spots on tlc using diisopropyl ether-isooctane (1 : 99), diisopropyl ether-isooctane (1 : 19) and diisopropyl ether-isooctane (1 : 9) as the developing solvent systems. The compound of the heavy end, with R_f 0.68, discussed in the present paper, was a pale yellow semi-solid (0.001%) (Found : C, 75.20 ; H, 11.10 ; S, 7.00 ; N, 6.20. C₂₈H₅₀N₂S calcd. C, 75.33 ; H, 11.21 ; S, 7.12 ; N, 6.28%).

Discussion

Chromatography of the feedstock (300-470° boiling fraction) on silica gel yielded best results with A/S 100 (Fig. 1). Elution with hexane removed 50.7% of waxy-white hydrocarbon (0.48% S) while benzene brought down 25% of a sulphur-rich residue (9.66% S). This residue (A) was processed further because of its appreciable yield and high sulphur content. It contained a good amount of aromatic hydrocarbons in addition to the desired sulphur compounds. A major portion of the former was removed by eluting with hexane-benzene (1 : 1) on activated alumina (A/S 200). Elution was continued till six coloured zones developed on the column (Fig. 2). Further elution was stopped to avoid diffusion.

The highest sulphur content found was for benzene extract of zone 2 (A_2) and methanol extract of zone 6 (A_{13}) 16 and 32%, respectively (Fig. 2). The residue A_2 , because of its appreciable yield, was processed further for obtaining the individual components. Qualitative analysis of this residue by tlc in diisopropyl ether-isooctane (2 : 3) revealed that it basically consisted of three zones, a blue fluorescent zone (under uv) with highest R_f value, a yellow fluorescent middle zone and a non-fluorescent residue at the base. The fractionation of the residue A_2 involved, firstly, the resolution of the fluorescent material in a very low polar solvent, without allowing the yellow zone from the base to move, followed by resolution of the latter using a higher polarity solvent but without disturbing the non-fluorescent residue. Repeated thin layer and column chromatography of the fractions, obtained as above, led to the isolation of a yellow semi-solid substance (R_f 0.68 in diisopropyl ether-heptane, 1 : 10, Fig 1). A medium band at 3390 cm^{-1} in the ir spectrum of the compound was assigned to the NH stretching vibration of a pyrrole nucleus supported by the bending vibration at 1076 cm^{-1} (medium) and its CH stretching at 3144 (medium), 1237 (weak) and 1040 cm^{-1} (weak to medium). The presence of pyrrole nucleus in the molecule was further supported by the ring stretching vibrations at 1540 (weak) and 1464 cm^{-1} (medium). The 3390 cm^{-1} band along with medium band at 3214 cm^{-1} was assigned to the NH stretching vibration of a primary amine. The strong bands at 2962 and 2888 cm^{-1} were of alkyl C—CH₃ and at 2928 and 2853 cm^{-1} of the alkyl C—CH₂ groups. A medium band at 3025 cm^{-1} was the =CH stretching vibration of a disubstituted olefin of the type RCH=CHR supported by its C=C vibrations at 1675 cm^{-1} (medium) and a weak band at 970 cm^{-1} of =CHR vibration. A doublet at 1398 and 1385 cm^{-1} suggested the presence of *gem*-dimethyl group, further supported by two weak bands as shoulders at 1215 and 1200 cm^{-1} . The bands at 1160 , 1140 , 1130 and 1100 cm^{-1} were the C—N stretching of an alkylamine. The 750 cm^{-1} band was assigned to the CS—C and/or the alkyl chain with $(\text{CH}_2)_{n \geq 4}$. The nmr spectrum of the compound showed a broad multiplet centered at δ 9.53 integrating for a single NH proton of pyrrole. The higher down-field value of the proton than that of an unsubstituted pyrrole suggested that NH was further conjugated with an electronegative group. A doublet at δ 7.30, JCH : NH^a ppm (one proton) was of the α -CH proton of pyrrole nucleus, while a broad multiplet between 5.00 and 5.83 (two protons) was assigned to the two olefinic protons and the multiplet centered at 3.60 to one proton situated between two electronegative groups E—CH—E. The δ 2.00-2.50 region showed one more multiplet of two protons on a carbon atom adjacent to an electronegative group (E—CH), while the four protons in the 1.65-2.00 region were β - to the electronegative group E—C—CH. The multiplet

centered at δ 0.98 integrated for 18 protons of CH₃ group and 21 protons of either alkyl-CH₂ or CH protons, respectively.

Thus from uv, ir and nmr spectra of the compound following information could be obtained : (i) the molecule contained a pyrrole nucleus with NH free and all positions except α -CH substituted, (ii) a primary amino group, (iii) an olefinic double bond of the type RCH=CHR conjugated to an electronegative group, (iv) at least one sulphur atom, (v) a —CH—E proton, and (vi) a E—CH—E and a long alkyl side chain.

All this information could be well fitted in the partial structure (1)

where X could be NH₂ or CH₃. The mass spectrum of the compound showed base peak at *m/e* 57 and the parent ion peak at 446. Combining elemental analysis with molecular ion peak of mass spectrum, the molecular formula of the compound obtained was C₂₈H₅₀N₂S, structure (2).

The number of unsaturations (rings and/or double bonds) in such a molecule is 5. All these five unsaturations are accounted in the structure (2).

As the nmr spectrum showed only four protons β to electronegative groups, two of which were S—C—CH₂ thus leaving two protons β to the pyrrole ring. Hence, these protons could be the NH₂ group protons. This position of the amino group was confirmed by the peak at *m/e* 151 which would have been formed by α -cleavage of the side chain at sulphur atom. The *m/e* 151 fragment lost two hydrogen atoms which resulted in further stabilisation of the ion by extension of conjugation, thus accounting for the higher relative abundance of the peak at *m/e* 149. The partial formula,

Scheme 1

Scheme 2

Scheme 3

having accounted for a fragment $\text{C}_7\text{H}_7\text{N}_2\text{S}$ in the molecule suggested that the side chain R was $(\text{C}_{28}\text{H}_{50}\text{N}_2\text{S}) - (\text{C}_7\text{H}_7\text{N}_2\text{S})$, i.e. $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{43}$. It was supported by a peak at m/e 295 which corresponded to a $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{43}$ ion (Scheme 1). That the molecule contained a propyl group at the 4th carbon atom from sulphur was indicated by the formation of m/e 284 fragment ion by the expulsion of propyl group by a five-membered ring mechanism. The position of sulphur atom in the compound was confirmed by a peak at m/e 153 which lost H_2S to give a peak at 112 (Scheme 2). Similarly, the position of NH_2 was supported by the loss of 16 mass unit ($-\text{NH}_2$ moiety) from the m/e 151 fragment to give 133 fragment (Scheme 1).

Scheme 3 systematically shows the fragmentation pattern of the alkyl side chain, thus confirming the various alkyl groups in the side chain. Formation of most of the fragment ions in the mass spectrum has been explained in Schemes 1, 2 and 3, justifying the positions of sulphur atom, amino group and various alkyl groups in the side chain. However, the structure of the compound proposed on the basis

of its elemental analysis and spectral data needs further confirmation by synthesis and chemical degradation which could not be done due to very small amount of the compound.

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References

1. Petrico Manual on "Impurities in Petroleum", Petrolite Corporation Laboratories, Petrico Division, Texas, 1968, 22.
2. C. LALAU, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1960, 22, 239.
3. D. M. JEWELL, G. K. HARTUNG, *J. Chem. Eng. Data*, 1964, 9, 297.
4. L. R. SNYDER, *Anal. Chem.*, 1969, 41, 1084.
5. L. R. SNYDER, *Acc. Chem. Res.*, 1970, 3, 290.
6. "Annual Book of ASTM Standards", 1975 American Society for Testing and Materials, Philadelphia, Part 23, Method, No. D 129.
7. "Annual Book of ASTM Standards", 1975, American Society for Testing and Materials, Philadelphia, Part 24, Method No. D 2784.